

A STUDY OF B.ED STUDENTS' PERCEPTION TOWARDS CHOICE BASED CREDIT SYSTEM

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Abstract

The purpose of the following paper is to B.Ed Students Perception towards Choice Based Credit System in Mumbai University. The sample consists of the 100 B.Ed students from Hansraj Jivandas college of Education. A self-made questionnaire was administered to study their perception towards Choice Based Credit System in Mumbai University. The perception was measured for the following aspects- coverage of course, efforts required, students benefit, & coping strategy. The results indicated that around 61% of the total samples were in favour of the credit based semester system. 55% of the total sample felt the extent of coverage of the course was very good. 54% of the students felt the extent of effort required is more in the Credit Based Semester System. 145 of the students found it easy to cope up were as 58% feel it is manageable and 8% find it difficult. The students found the system to be very beneficial but may be it still needs to be managed well with respect to the time factor as the admissions are very late and by the time students are admitted there is hardly any time left for completing the activities in the first semester. Every new system has some teething problems but with time these too will be overcome.

Key Words: - *B.Ed Students Perception, Credit Based Semester System, , Course coverage, efforts, benefits & coping.*

Introduction

There is a necessity to develop a Choice-Based Credit System (CBCS) in tune with global trends and the adoption of a sound grading system for reflecting learner performance. Time and again The University Grants Commission (UGC), the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC), the Distance Education Council (DEC) and National Knowledge Commission (NKC) have stressed on improving the quality and effectiveness of the Higher education system by making it more student friendly.

Recommendation of the UGC in its *Action Plan for Academic and Administrative Reforms* (Ref. UGC letters January 2008; March 2009)

“..... Curricular flexibility and learners’ mobility is an issue that warrants our urgent attention. These can be addressed by introducing credit based courses and credit accumulation. In order to provide with some degree of flexibility to learners, we need to provide for course duration in terms of credit hours and also a minimum as well as a maximum permissible span of time in which a course can be completed by a learner... The Choice-Based Credit System (CBCS) imminently fits into the emerging socioeconomic milieu, and could effectively respond to the educational and occupational aspirations of the upcoming generations. In view of this, institutions of higher education in India would do well to invest thought and resources into introducing CBCS. Aided by modern communication and information technology, CBCS has a high probability to be operationalised efficiently and effectively — elevating learners, institutions and higher education system in the country to newer heights...”

Thus to meet the demands of the present situation Mumbai University also implemented the CBCS from the academic year 2011-2012.

Concept of CBCS:-

CBCS essentially implies a redefining of the curriculum into smaller measurable entities or ‘modules’ with the hours required for studying/‘learning’ these – not ‘teaching’ - being at the primary focus and the development of a mechanism whereby these modules can be combined in different ways so as to qualify for a Certificate, Diploma or Degree. In a sense, therefore, the completion of a single ‘Module’ of learning can pave the way for learning other modules either

in the same institution or elsewhere and a combination of modules in keeping with the needs and interests of the learners illustrates the much talked about 'cafeteria approach' to learning with the Learner at the centre stage of all academic transactions.

Advantages of the Credit System

- Represents a much-required shift in focus from teacher-centric to learner-centric education since the workload estimated is based on the investment of time in learning, not in teaching.
- Helps to record course work and to document learner workload realistically since all activities are taken into account - not only the time learners spend in lectures or seminars but also the time they need for individual learning and the preparation of examinations etc.
- Helps self-paced learning.
- Affords more flexibility to the learners allowing them to choose inter-disciplinary courses, change majors, programmes, etc.
- 'Learner Autonomy' by allowing them to choose according to their own learning needs, interests and aptitudes.
- Facilitates Learner Mobility. Offers the opportunity to study at different times and in different places. Credits earned at one institution can be transferred to another.

Need of the study:

As CBCS is still in its infancy stage thus it becomes imperative for the developers and deliverers to have better understanding of how students perceive and react system because ultimately they are one of the most important stakeholders of the education system. Thus it is important to study the students' perceptions towards Credit Based Semester System

Statement of the problem:

A Study of B.Ed Students' Perception towards Choice Based Credit System introduced by Mumbai University in the academic year 2011-12 for the one year B.Ed program.

Objectives of the study:

- To study the perception of the B.Ed students towards the CBCS.

- To study the extent of coverage of the course syllabus.
- To study the extent to which the students benefit from the CBCS.
- To study whether the students find the CBCS easy or difficult to cope up with.

Operational definitions:**Choice-Based Credit System (CBCS):**

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Program:

A Program is a set of courses that are linked together in an academically meaningful way and generally ends with the award of a Certificate or Diploma or Degree depending on the level of knowledge attained and the total duration of study. For example the Bachelor of Education (B.Ed) program.

Perception:

is defined as what the B.Ed student feels, thinks and views about the CBCS introduced by the Mumbai University in the B.Ed program.

Significance of the study:

The study helped to know the students perceptions towards the CBCS. The study will provide the data for the policy makers and designers of the CBCS so as to know its effectiveness from students' perspective.

Scope and Limitations:

The study measures the perception of the B.Ed students who had completed the B.ED program with the implementation of the CBCS in Mumbai University for the academic year 2011-12. The study is restricted to B.Ed students of **Hansraj Jivandas College of Education**. The study is limited to measuring the B.Ed students' perception towards CBCS for the following aspects- coverage of course, efforts required, students benefit, & coping strategy. The study is

limited to measuring the B.Ed students' perception by using the researcher made paper-pencil test only.

Methodology of the study:

Survey method is used to study the B.Ed students' perception towards CBCS .

Sample and sample size:

The sample consists of 100 B.Ed students of Hansraj Jivandas college of Education.

Sampling Technique:

For the present study Incidental and Purposive sampling technique was used.

Tool and data gathering procedure:

A five point likert rating scale was prepared by the researcher to study B.Ed students' perception towards CBCS . The 20 item tool was administered to the students at the end of the B.Ed program. Students were given clear instructions and a time period of 20 minutes to respond to the tool. The scale has the ranging from 5 to 1. where score 5 represents very good, 4 -good, 3 uncertain/no comment , 2 satisfied and 1 unsatisfied response.

Analysis of the data: The responses given by the total sample for each aspect was converted into percentages.

Table 1.1

Students Responses in Percentages

Items	Students Responses				
	Very Good %	Good %	Uncertain %	Satisfied %	Unsatisfied %
Perception of the B.Ed students towards the CBCS	61	21	0	18	0
Extent of coverage of the course syllabus.	55	34	0	11	0

Extent to which the students benefit from the CBCS.	70	24	0	6	0
Whether the students find the CBCS easy or difficult to cope up with.	60	8	0	0	32

Major Findings and Discussion:

61% of the students find the CBCS to be very good, 21% good, 18% satisfactory. The reasons could be the examination load is divided into two semesters and they can even appear for ATKT if they are not able to clear the papers in the first attempt. Also they don't waste their entire year and don't have to appear for all the papers again. The credits for the other papers and the practical's which they have cleared is carried forward. As compared to the previous system the students save on time, energy and money. Students need to concentrate only on four papers in first semester which reduces their stress levels. 18% students find it satisfactory the reason could be some students find it really difficult to cope with the CBCS as the admission procedure in B.Ed goes on till the August end or sometimes even in September. Students who are admitted late to the program really find it difficult to cope up with the theory and practical's as they get very less time to prepare as compared to other students who are admitted right from the beginning.

70% of the students feel the CBCS is very beneficial for them as it helps them to carry forward the credit points.

55% of the students the extent of coverage of the course is more in CBCS as compared to the time available. The reason could be the syllabus for every course is very vast as compared to the previous system where they had the flexibility of covering the syllabus throughout the year.

More than 60% of the students find the CBCS manageable were as 32% find it difficult. The reason could be the late admissions of the students.

Conclusion and Suggestions:-

We can definitely overcome the challenges and the problems faced in the CBCS by adopting few strategies like orienting the students through workshops, expert talks regarding the benefits of CBCS as the students till their graduation or post Graduation have been accustomed to the traditional system of education. Also the admission process in B.Ed needs serious attention from the authorities if the students are admitted into the program by the month of June they automatically have enough time for both the semesters. Another important area is proper guidance and counseling for the students especially in case of late admissions so as to foster positive attitude and reduce their anxiety by providing all the resources such as proper orientation to the topics what they have missed, study material, constructive feedback.

There is always going to be a lot of resistance when bringing any change in the system especially to the system to which we are attuned from our childhood. But that should not deter us from bringing new and positive changes keeping in mind the global trend and the needs of the present generation. We all need to work in collaboration to make the system effective and a great success.

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